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Title: Cleanability of Milk Fouling Deposits on Inner Stainless Steel Tubing Surfaces Prepared by Magnetic Abrasive Finishing

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Abstract: Milk fouling deposits are a serious technical and economic problem for the dairy industry. The proteins and minerals in milk form deposits on the surface of stainless steel equipment. The Magnetic Abrasive Finishing (MAF) process was used to produce highly finished inner surfaces of stainless steel tubes to compare to tubes with conventional inner surfaces. Fouling and cleaning tests were carried out using an experimental loop including the stainless steel tubes with different surface roughness profiles. Data showed that the smoothly finished inner surface ($R_a=0.037 \mu\text{m}$) of stainless steel tubes significantly improved the cleanability of milk residues. The results may indicate that the cleanability of non-protein components of milk residue is affected by surface roughness. Key words: magnetic abrasive finishing, milk fouling, stainless steel tubing, surface roughness.μμμμμμμμμμ

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Dear Editor,

Please find enclosed our manuscript entitled “Cleanability of Milk Fouling Deposits on Inner Stainless Steel Tubing Surfaces Prepared by Magnetic Abrasive Finishing”, which we would like to submit for publication as an original article in *Biosystems Engineering*. The manuscript word count is 3672 words.

We confirm that this manuscript has not been published elsewhere. All authors have approved the manuscript and agree with submission to *Biosystems Engineering*. The authors have no conflicts of interest to declare.

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We shall look forward to hearing from you at your earliest convenience.

Yours sincerely,

Ikko Ihara

Associate Prof.

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- Magnetic abrasive finishing (MAF) is a precise method for inner surface polishing.
- Stainless steel tubings with a highly smooth surface were prepared by MAF.
- We evaluated the cleanability of milk foulings on different inner surfaces.
- The highly finished surface improves the cleanability of milk foulings.

Cleanability of Milk Fouling Deposits on Inner Stainless Steel Tubing Surfaces Prepared by Magnetic Abrasive Finishing

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Abstract

Milk fouling deposits are a serious technical and economic problem for the dairy industry. The proteins and minerals in milk form deposits on the surface of stainless steel equipment. The Magnetic Abrasive Finishing (MAF) process was used to produce highly finished inner surfaces of stainless steel tubes to compare to tubes with conventional inner surfaces. Fouling and cleaning tests were carried out using an experimental loop including the stainless steel tubes with different surface roughness profiles. Data showed that the smoothly finished inner surface ($R_a=0.037\ \mu\text{m}$) of stainless steel tubes significantly improved the cleanability of milk residues. The results may indicate that the cleanability of non-protein components of milk residue is affected by surface roughness.

Key words: magnetic abrasive finishing, milk fouling, stainless steel tubing, surface roughness.

1. Introduction

The safety of milk is important for consumers of dairy products. Bacteria and organic residues collect easily on the surfaces of handling and processing equipment. Milk is a complicated biological fluid and contains proteins, ash, and minerals (Bansal and Chen, 2006) which frequently foul the stainless steel tubing in handling and processing equipment. Calcium phosphate and whey protein are the main components of these milk deposits (Rosmaninho and Melo, 2008). Cleaning the fouling is a time-consuming and energy-intensive process which requires substantial quantities of water and chemicals (Balasubramanian and Puri, 2009). Fouling-related costs include additional energy, equipment, labor, chemicals, environmental impacts, and lost productivity. The hygienic quality of food processing is related to cleanability, and the surface roughness of the stainless steel plates has been shown to be an important factor in cleaning yoghurt-soil (Leclercq-Perlat and Lalande, 1994) and buttermilk residue (Frank and Chmielewski, 2001) and in removing adhering *Staphylococcus* (Ortega et al., 2008). The R_a value, which is the arithmetical mean of the surface roughness, is

widely used as an index of surface characteristics. The EHEDG (European Hygienic Engineering and Design Group) and 3-A Sanitary Standards (McLean, Virginia, USA) have established a requirement of an R_a value of 0.8 μm or less for the stainless steel surfaces on food equipment (EHEDG, 1993; Schonrock, 2012). However, many investigations have failed in demonstrating any clear relationship between R_a values and surface cleanability (Jullien et al., 2002). Comparing with flat plates, stainless steel tubes have not been sufficiently investigated due to the difficulty of finishing smoother inner surfaces and assessing cleanability.

A magnetic abrasive finishing (MAF) technology has been studied for finishing inner surfaces that are hard to reach by conventional techniques (Yamaguchi et al., 2001; Yamaguchi et al., 2007). This MAF technology has the potential to reduce the surface roughness on the inside of the stainless steel tubing used in the dairy industry. The purpose of this study was to find the relationship between the cleanability of milk foulings and the surface roughness of stainless steel tubes, including some of which are smoother because they have been polished by the magnetic abrasive finishing technology.

2. Material and Methods

2.1. Preparation of stainless steel tubing

Stainless steel tubes with various internal surface textures were prepared to investigate the effects of the surface roughness on the cleanability of the milk fouling deposits on the inner surface of the tubes. The experiments were conducted with 304 stainless steel tubes ($\varnothing 12.7$ mm outer diameter, $\varnothing 10.9$ mm inner diameter, 1.83 m long) purchased from the McMaster-Carr Supply Company (Atlanta, USA) with two different as-received surface roughnesses ($\sim 3 \mu\text{m } R_z$ and $\sim 30 \mu\text{m } R_z$). These tubes were sectioned to be 65 mm long, and three tubes of each roughness were prepared for the experiments.

In addition, the inner surfaces of another set of three tubes with as-received surface roughness of $\sim 3 \mu\text{m } R_z$ were made smoother by finishing using an MAF process. The MAF process has advantages of finishing areas that are difficult to process by conventional finishing technologies, such as the interiors of long, bent, and capillary tubes (Yamaguchi et al., 2001, 2004, and 2007). The MAF process can potentially be applied to the variety of tubes used in milking systems.

Figure 1 shows a schematic of the MAF processing principle and a photograph of the MAF machine used. The MAF process uses a magnetic field to manipulate magnetic abrasive, which is introduced into the tube and suspended by magnetic force according to the lines of magnetic force produced by the permanent magnets placed outside the tube. As the tube rotates, the magnetic abrasive suspended by the magnetic field exhibits relative motion against the tube surface, finishing the inner surface of the tube.

It is commonly known that the magnetic force F acting on the magnetic abrasive can be obtained using the following equation:

$$F = V\chi H \cdot \nabla H \quad (1)$$

where V is the volume of the magnetic abrasive, χ is the magnetic susceptibility of the abrasive, H is the magnetic field strength, and ∇H is the gradient of the magnetic field.

In a magnetic field, the magnetic abrasive forms chains that conform to the target surface while finishing. This allows the finishing of complex surfaces and surfaces, such as tube interiors, that are difficult to access using conventional finishing operations. The abrasive motion, and thus the resulting roughness and topography, can be controlled by adjusting the parameters in Eq. (1) which affect the magnetic force.

In this paper, two pairs of neodymium (Nd-Fe-B) permanent magnets (18×12×10 mm) were used as magnetic field generators to generate the magnetic field needed for attracting the magnetic abrasive to the finishing area. An area 70 mm long inside each tube was finished under the conditions shown in Table 1. After finishing, the tubes were cleaned with ethanol for 20 min using an ultrasonic cleaner and finished portions cut to 65 mm long were used for the milk cleanability tests.

A total of nine tubes representing three levels of surface roughness (three samples each) were prepared for the study in this paper. Surface profiles of these tubes were measured with a surface roughness tester (Mitutoyo, SJ-400). The roughness, measured as the arithmetic average deviation R_a and the average maximum height R_z , are shown in Table 2.

2.2 Static test for the cleanability of Ca^{2+} deposition

Besides the dynamic tests with moving milk which constitute the bulk of this paper, static tests were conducted for the evaluation of the cleanability of calcium deposits. Half tubes were produced by slicing tubes longitudinally using an IsoMet Low Speed Saw (Buehler, USA). Tubes composed of roughness type A ($0.037 \mu\text{m } R_a$) and type B ($0.37 \mu\text{m } R_a$) were sonicated in an ultrasonic cleaner (see Table 2 for details of pipe roughness). The half tubes were dipped in whole milk diluted with deionized water (1:10) to simulate milk fouling. After immersing each tube in diluted milk for 120 s, each tube was placed in a tube with 13 mL of deionized water and then sonicated for twenty minutes to simulate cleaning. To determine the cleanability of each tube, Ca^{2+} deposition on the washed half tube was measured with a self-referencing (SR) microsensor following the procedures in McLamore and Porterfield (2011) and Sun et al. (2012). SR is a technique that measures differential ion concentration (ΔC) while oscillating a microsensor between two locations (termed near pole and far pole) at a fixed excursion distance (ΔX). Flux (J) is calculated based on Fick's first law of diffusion ($J = -D \cdot \Delta C \cdot \Delta X^{-1}$).

First, microelectrodes were fabricated by tapering non-filamented 1.5 mm borosilicate glass capillaries (World Precision Instruments) on a Sutter P-97 horizontal puller (Flaming-Brown, Sutter Instrument Co.) to obtain a shank of 4.0 mm and a tip diameter of 3 μm . Prior to use, pulled

capillaries were backfilled with electrolyte (10 μM CaCl_2), and then front filled with Ca^{2+} selective ionophore under a microscope (Sun et al., 2012). Microelectrodes were inserted into a half-cell microelectrode holder fitted with an electrochemically plated Ag/AgCl wire. Reference probes were fabricated by injecting a solution of 3 M KCl with 3% agar into 1.5 mm polyethylene tubing inserted into a microelectrode holder half cell (World Precision Instruments).

For measuring flux, a Ca^{2+} microsensor was positioned within 500 nm of the surface using a computer-controlled stepper motor system fixed to a vibration table/Faraday cage that contains a microscope (Fig. 2). Computer controlled stepper motors were used to oscillate the microsensor (50 μm) perpendicular to the longitudinal tube surface while continuously recording differential concentration. The molecular diffusion coefficient for Ca^{2+} used in all analysis was $4.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ sec}^{-1}$). The measurements were repeated three times.

2.3. Workpiece cleaning for dynamic test

Before each fouling test, all stainless steel tubes were cleaned according to the following procedure: (1) sonicated in an ultrasonic cleaner with a 2.0% w/v neutral detergent (RBS 35, Sigma-Aldrich) for 10 min; (2) sonicated with recycling-isopropanol for 10 min; and (3) sonicated with isopropanol for 10 min. All tubes were dried completely in air before the fouling tests.

2.4. Fouling and cleaning procedures for dynamic test

Fouling experiments with whole milk were carried out in two experimental loops consisting of one water bath, one peristaltic pump with two heads, and 10 tubes under test (Fig. 3). The experimental apparatus was set in an incubator at 23°C. The fouling experiment was carried out with whole milk at 40°C and run for 8 hr with a 7 min-on / 3 min-off cycle, at a flow rate of 0.4 L/min, which corresponds to the flow rate in a typical dairy piping system between a milking robot and a bulk cooler (Hoshiba et al., 2000). To avoid the effect of the position on the flow path, the tubes were located randomly with respect to internal surface roughness on each run. After the fouling test, the connected stainless steel tubes with milk deposits were kept in the loops for 48 hr. During the 48 hours, the workpieces are connected horizontally to the experimental loop with milk. The height of milk solution in the horizontal pipes is adjusted to half of inside diameter after the milk circulation.

Cleaning experiments with deionized water at 20°C were carried out in the experimental equipment loops. Deionized water was flushed for 5 min at a mean flow rate of 0.4 L/min without circulation. After the cleaning test, the test pipes were dismantled from the experimental loops and dried in air for 24 hr in a incubator at 23°C

2.5. Evaluation of residues on internal surface at dynamic test

To evaluate the cleanability of the milk foulings in the tubes, we measured amounts of milk

residues and residual proteins on internal surface of the tubes. All the stainless steel tubes were washed with 13 ml of deionized water using an ultrasonic cleaner for 20 min. The light absorbance at 660 nm of the washing solution was measured using a spectrophotometer (Hitachi, U-5100) to determine the milk residues that were removed by the ultrasonic cleaner. The sonication and absorbance measurement were carried out seven times on each workpiece. The absorbance value at 660 nm was related to the milk concentration in the diluted milk sample within in the range of 0.075-1.5% (v/v). For the quantification of residual proteins, all the stainless steel tubes were washed with 13 ml of deionized water using an ultrasonic cleaner for 50 min in three runs. The washed solution and Bradford reagent (Sigma-Aldrich) were mixed and then measured using the spectrophotometer to determine protein concentration. The sonication and absorbance measurement were carried out three times on each workpiece. The protein calibration had been carried out using bovine serum albumin (BSA) as the standard protein.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Deposition and detachment of calcium on the static test

Lower magnitudes of Ca^{2+} surface flux were measured from the magnetically-finished smoother surface (roughness A) compared with the non-polished surface (roughness B) for the half tubes subjected to the static tests. Fig. 4 shows the results after fouling and after simulated cleaning. It can be seen that the deposition flux on the non-polished surface was higher, perhaps because the rougher surface has more surface area to act as nucleation sites for Ca^{2+} deposition. The amorphous calcium particles in dairy solutions are easily trapped in rougher sites and contribute to accelerating the deposit buildup (Jimenez et al., 2013). These results indicate that the magnetically-polished smoother surface with a R_a less than $0.8 \mu\text{m}$ reduced initial fouling and enhanced the cleanability.

3.2. Cleanability of milk fouling on the dynamic test

The absorbance of the washing solution indicated the concentrations of the milk residues that were removed from the internal surfaces using the ultrasonic cleaner. The absorbance values of the washing solution from inner surface in five trials are shown in Fig. 5. The data indicated that milk fouling levels in each trial were not consistent due to the non-constant milk components including protein, mineral, sugar and fat. We calculated the relative absorbance value to correct the differences in each cleanability trial. The data are expressed as relative milk concentration, with workpiece C being set to 1.0 in each trial.

Figure 6 shows the relationship between relative milk concentrations in washed solution and surface roughness R_a . The data showed that higher cleanability of milk foulings was obtained with decreasing R_a . The effect of surface roughness R_a on the cleanability was analyzed by Tukey's multiple comparison test. Differences in cleanability of milk foulings were significant between workpieces A ($0.037 \mu\text{m } R_a$) and B ($0.37 \mu\text{m } R_a$) and between workpieces B ($0.37 \mu\text{m } R_a$) and C (3.7

$\mu\text{m } R_a$). A clear correlation between surface roughness and cleanability of milk fouling from the surface was obtained. EHEDG specifies that the product contact surface should have a surface finish of $0.8 \mu\text{m } R_a$ or better for large surface areas (EHEDG, 1993). Lelieveld and Mostert (2003) noted that the cold rolled steel has a roughness of $0.2\text{-}0.5 \mu\text{m } R_a$, and does not have to be polished to meet EHEDG surface requirements. The data showed that the MAF can make a smoother internal surface of tube that has less than $0.8 \mu\text{m } R_a$ value, and the process provided the higher cleanability of milk foulings in the workpieces A ($0.037 \mu\text{m } R_a$).

The hydrodynamic effects are an important parameter for cleaning efficiency and the wall shear stress is the most suitable criterion governing the removal of foulings (Lelièvre et al., 2003). Leclercq-Perlat and Lalande (1994) reported that milk soil was found to be more difficult to remove with increasing surface roughness of SUS304L plate (R_a ranging from 0.11 to $0.3 \mu\text{m}$), because milk soiling attachment in pits and crevices on rough surface experienced weak cleaning forces compared with smooth surfaces. Jullien et al. (2002) indicated that surface irregularities with a few wider deep scratches or crevices might provide protection from wall shear stress to entrapped bacterial spores. Frank and Chmielewski (2000) had shown that surface roughness measurements of finished flat steel surfaces that are associated with defects, as determined by the mean peak valley height value R_z , were significantly correlated with cleanability of buttermilk-soiled surfaces. Some research studies have shown that surface roughness as indicated by R_a does not affect the cleanability of milk foulings (Yoon et al., 1994; Barns et al., 1999; Jullien et al., 2002). In the static condition of rinsing or cleaning, shear stress is not sufficient to detach fouling deposits from surface. Our result indicated that a higher cleanability of milk foulings was obtained by wall shear stress in a cleaning flow in stainless steel tubes with the smooth surface roughness reduced by MAF.

3.3. Cleanability of milk proteins on the dynamic test

Milk contains approximately 3.4% whey proteins, 4.8% lactose, 0.8% minerals, and 3.9% fat (Bansal and Chen, 2006). The whey proteins are composed of casein, β -lactoglobulin and α -lactalbumin. Whey proteins and calcium phosphate are main components of milk foulings on stainless steel surfaces (Rosmaninho and Melo, 2008). Figure 7 shows protein concentrations in washed solution from internal surface of tube analyzed by Bradford method. The data showed that protein concentration levels were not consistent due to the unstable milk fouling level. Figure 8 shows the relationship between the relative protein concentrations in the washed solution and the surface roughness R_a . The data are expressed as relative protein concentrations, with workpiece C being 1.0 in each trial. The data showed no clear correlation between surface roughness and cleanability of milk proteins from the surface. These results indicated that the surface roughness might have influenced the removal of the non-protein milk components such as calcium, but not the milk proteins, from the stainless tube surface. It is known that calcium phosphate has also lower

cleanability in milk components. The aggregates of calcium phosphate form at 44°C (Rosmaninho and Melo, 2008), which is higher than that of our fouling experiments. It is believed that the deposition of calcium phosphate aggregates in the experiments had little influence on the cleanability of surfaces.

4. Conclusions

This research investigates the relationship between internal surface roughness of stainless steel tubing and the cleanability of milk fouling. Stainless steel tubes with an internal surface roughness of $0.037 \mu\text{m } R_a$ were prepared by a magnetic assisted finishing process. The results of this work can be summarized as follows:

- (1) The MAF process improved the surface roughness of internal stainless steel tube to 10 times smoother than the sanitary regulations.
- (2) Ca^{2+} deposition on the smooth surface ($0.037 \mu\text{m } R_a$) was reduced comparing with the rougher surface ($0.37 \mu\text{m } R_a$) on the static test.
- (3) The dynamic cleaning tests demonstrated a clear correlation between the surface roughness and cleanability of milk foulings from the tube surface.
- (4) The experiments demonstrated that the tube surface roughness affected the cleanability of non-protein components, but not the protein components of milk. As a result, smoothing the tube surface enhanced the cleanability of the milk foulings from the tube surface.

The cleaning solution on the dynamic tests was performed under laminar condition. Further research under turbulence flow is needed to establish relationships between the surface roughness and the cleanability.

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Table 1 Tube finishing conditions

Workpiece	304 Stainless steel tube (OD: $\varnothing 12.7$ mm, ID: $\varnothing 10.7$ mm, Length 130 mm) Finished length: 65 mm
Workpiece revolution	1800 min^{-1}
Mixed-type magnetic abrasive	Steel grit (700 μm mean diameter): 0.48 g Iron particles (177-590 μm diameter): 0.48 g Magnetic abrasive (80 μm mean dia.): 0.24 g
Pole-tip geometry	
Pole-tip feed	1 mm/s
Workpiece-pole-tip clearance	1 mm
Lubricant	Soluble-type barrel finishing compound (pH: 9.5, Viscosity: 755 mPa·s at 30°C)
Processing time	47.5 min

Table 2 Surface roughness of tested workpieces

Workpiece	A (polished)	B (unpolished)	C (unpolished)
R_z (μm)	0.26 ± 0.07	2.4 ± 0.4	23.8 ± 2.0
R_a (μm)	0.037 ± 0.001	0.37 ± 0.07	3.7 ± 0.4

Fig. 1 MAF processing principle and machine.

Fig. 2 Self referencing (SR) microsensor.

Fig. 3 Experimental setup.

Fig. 4 Ca^{2+} surface flux changes on the static test. Error bar shows standard error.

Fig. 5 Milk concentrations in washed solution from internal surface on each trial. Error bar shows standard error.

Fig. 6 Relationship between relative milk concentrations in washed solution and surface roughness R_a . Error bar shows standard error. Different letters indicate significant differences according to the Tukey-Kramer multiple range test ($P < 0.05$).

Fig. 7 Protein concentrations in washed solution from internal surface on each trial. Error bar shows standard error.

Fig. 8 Relationship between relative protein concentration in washed solution and surface roughness R_a . Error bar shows standard error. Same letter is not significantly different according to the Tukey-Kramer multiple range test ($P < 0.05$).

Figure1

Figure2

Figure 3

Figure4

Figure5

Figure6

Figure7

Figure8

